

Band gap widening of chalcopyrite solar cell absorbers after potassium fluoride treatment

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The implementation of potassium fluoride treatments as a new doping and surface modification procedure in chalcopyrite absorber preparation has recently gained much interest since it led to new record efficiencies for this kind of solar cells. In the present work, Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ absorbers have been evaporated on Na containing Mo/soda-lime glass substrates. We report on compositional and electronic changes of the Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ absorber surface as a result of a post deposition treatment with KF (KF PDT). In particular, by comparing standard X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and synchrotron-based hard X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (HAXPES) we are able to confirm a strong Cu depletion in the absorbers after the KF PDT which is limited to the very near surface region. As a result of the Cu depletion, we find a change of the valence band structure and a shift of the valence band edge by approximately 0.4 eV to lower binding energies which is tentatively explained by a band gap widening as expected for Cu deficient compounds. The KF PDT increased the open circuit voltage by 60-70 mV compared to the untreated absorbers, while the fill factor deteriorated.

THE MANUSCRIPT

Introduction

The potential of chalcopyrite solar cells and modules as a versatile, low-cost thin film technology has long been proven and is confirmed by recent developments and efficiency improvements [1,2,3] which are accompanied by the build-up of production capacities in the GW regime [4]. By achieving 20.8% maximum conversion efficiency the anterior gap to polycrystalline silicon technologies could finally be surpassed. While the importance of sodium for the doping, growth and interdiffusion kinetics in chalcopyrite solar cell absorbers has long been discussed and established [5-7], less attention has been paid to the implementation of other alkaline metals in the past. Recent findings of Würz, Laemmler et al. showed that similar to sodium, potassium can be introduced into the chalcopyrite absorber during growth [8] or in a post deposition treatment [9] (PDT) in order to enhance the net charge carrier concentration in the absorber. In addition to this, a PDT with KF of Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ (CIGS) absorbers grown by a three-stage process on polyimide foil has been established by Chirila et al. and led to efficiencies up to 20.4% [2]. They found an influence of the KF treatment not only on the bulk of the absorber but more importantly a modification of the CIGS surface. In particular they found a modified interface with a pronounced Cu depletion and assumed a better incorporation of Cd into the absorber surface during the buffer deposition to be the reason for the efficiency improvement. In a recent publication, Pianezzi et al. suggested stronger type inversion as a result of the KF PDT being responsible for reduced interface recombination and better device performance [10]. We find evidence for a lowered valence band edge at the KF treated CIGS surface and add the idea of an increased band gap region whose effect will be discussed in this work.

We concentrate on the influence of KF PDTs on the surface of evaporated CIGS absorbers and investigate the changes in surface composition and valence band structure, relating them also to device performance. The surface sensitivity of X-ray

photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) makes it an ideal tool to study compositional changes at the absorber surface. Using brilliant synchrotron-based radiation with tunable excitation energy this tool becomes even more powerful as it allows the variation of the information depth. We use a standard laboratory Mg K α X-ray source in combination with the high kinetic energy XPS end station (HIKE) at the KMC-1 beamline at the BESSY II synchrotron facility for the acquisition of XPS data. For further information on the HIKE setup the interested reader is referred to reference [11]. Special attention is paid to changes in the band structure of the absorber at the surface, as minor changes at the absorber/buffer interface can have tremendous effects on the device performance, especially in view of potential interface recombination. Here, we compare the valence band structure of samples with and without KF PDT from data acquired at the HIKE endstation and data obtained with ultraviolet photoelectron spectroscopy (UPS).

Experimental details and results

CIGS was deposited on Mo/soda-lime glass by a standard three-stage process at a maximum temperature of 560°C and with a [Cu]/([Ga]+[In]) (CGI) ratio of 0.80 and a [Ga]/([Ga]+[In]) (GGI) of 0.31. For more details on the absorber process, see reference [12]. After absorber deposition, KF was evaporated on non-heated CIGS absorber layers in a separate evaporation chamber with a targeted thickness of 15 nm and 25 nm, respectively. The KF was then diffused *ex situ* into the absorber for 12.5 min at a substrate temperature of 350°C in an evaporation chamber used for absorber deposition while evaporating Se at the same rate used for the absorber deposition. After KF PDT, two different cleaning methods were applied to remove residual KF from the absorber surface: I) DI water rinsing: samples were simply washed in de-ionized (DI) water or II) HCl etching: samples were etched in HCl (1%, 1 min) before rinsing in DI water. Samples were then further processed with a standard CdS buffer deposited in a chemical bath, followed by a sputtered i-ZnO/ZnO:Al front contact and a Ni/Al contact grid. The cell area of the completed solar cells was either 0.5 cm² or 1.0 cm². The IV-characteristics of these devices were measured under simulated AM1.5 illumination and compared to untreated CIGS references built from the same absorber batch. The average solar cell parameters of the resulting devices are summarized in Tab. 1. While in our case the KF PDT did not lead to an efficiency improvement, mainly because of a ~10% decrease in the fill factor, the treatment did positively affect the open circuit voltage (V_{OC}) and led to an increase of 60-70 mV for all KF PDT samples, independent of the applied KF thickness and cleaning method.

TABLE I. Average solar cell parameters of two untreated Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ references and samples with 15 nm or 25 nm KF PDT and with H₂O or HCl cleaning. (100 words)

Sample	V_{OC} (mV)	j_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)	η (%)
No KF PDT	595	31.3	72.6	13.6
No KF PDT	611	31.2	73.7	14.1
15 nm KF H ₂ O	668	30.3	62.7	12.7
15 nm KF HCl	641	30.9	56.8	11.3
25 nm KF H ₂ O	668	29.4	60.4	11.9
25 nm KF HCl	663	30.2	58.6	11.8

The observed V_{OC} increase compares to -but is slightly less than- the open circuit voltage increase of up to 111 mV observed by Laemmle et al. when they investigated CIGS absorbers prepared on alkaline-free alumina substrates with and without KF PDT [8]. However, it is quite remarkable that for the samples presented in this work, the V_{OC} increases despite the fact that

samples were prepared on sodium containing glass substrates which already act as an alkaline source during growth. In fact, capacitance voltage measurements at room temperature show that the net charge carrier concentrations increased only slightly from $3 \times 10^{15}/\text{cm}^3$ - $4 \times 10^{15}/\text{cm}^3$ for the presented references to $4 \times 10^{15}/\text{cm}^3$ - $5 \times 10^{15}/\text{cm}^3$ after the KF PDT. This demonstrates that the observed V_{OC} increase cannot be attributed to an enhancement in the charge carrier density in the bulk of the absorber material.

For the surface analysis, an absorber sample from the same batch was prepared with a 25 nm KF layer and identical process parameters for the *ex situ* in-diffusion process as described above. The sample was then characterized by XPS with the Mg $K\alpha$ X-ray source and compared to an untreated CIGS reference. Pronounced K 1s, F 1s and Na 1s signals could be detected on the KF PDT treated sample. Both, the untreated and KF PDT sample were then directly transferred into an oxygen free glovebox and there cut into two pieces. One piece of each sample was then rinsed with DI water, whereas the other one was etched in HCl with the cleaning procedures described above. Afterwards, the four samples were directly transferred back into the XPS chamber without air exposure. All liquids used for these procedures were bubbled with ultrapure nitrogen to make them oxygen-free. In addition to laboratory XPS, the KF treated and the untreated CIGS, both after DI water rinsing, were analyzed in the HIKE end station using synchrotron radiation with an energy of 2100 eV. Fig. 1 shows XPS survey spectra using laboratory Mg $K\alpha$ excitation, with comparable In and Se signal intensities for all four cleaned samples. From the extinction of the K 1s and F 1s signals we conclude that both cleaning procedures are effective methods to remove the residual KF, although traces of K could still be found in prolonged detail spectra (not shown) on the sample simply rinsed in DI water. For this sample also an increased O 1s signal is observed, most probably a surface oxidation effect of the *ex situ* KF preparation method applied here. The surface oxides were removed for both samples that had been etched in HCl.

The most distinct changes were observed for the Cu signals, which are strongly decreased for the KF treated samples as can be seen in Fig 1. In Fig. 2 detail spectra of the In $3d_{5/2}$ and the Cu $2p_{3/2}$ core levels of an untreated and a KF treated sample are shown. For clarity, only the spectra of the two samples rinsed in DI water are displayed as representatives; the sample etched in HCl showed similar signal intensities. In order to get an estimate of the Cu/In ratio at the surface, the peaks were fitted with a Voigt function to obtain the peak area. The Cu/In signal ratio of the untreated reference sample is compared to that of the KF PDT sample in Fig. 2 c) and d). As can be seen, when using the laboratory X-ray source with 1253.6 eV excitation energy, the surface Cu/In signal ratio of the treated sample is diminished to less than 10% of the reference sample. With an excitation energy of 2100 eV the Cu/In signal ratio of the KF PDT sample is still much lower than the reference (~55% of the reference value), but the decrease is not as strong as with the laboratory based X-ray source. There are two main differences between the two measurements: firstly, the laboratory X-ray source averages over many more local inhomogeneities due to a larger beam spot compared to the synchrotron source; secondly, the escape depth of the involved photoelectrons differs, as higher excitation energies lead to an increasing inelastic mean free path (IMFP). The IMFP calculated with the TPP2M formula of Tanuma et al. [13] increases from 0.8nm (1253.6 eV) to 2.2nm (2100 eV) for the Cu 2p peak, and from 1.7nm to 2.9nm for In 3d photoelectrons. Based on these findings, we confirm that as a consequence of the KF PDT, the CIGS absorber surface becomes nearly completely depleted of Cu in a region that stretches only a few nanometers into the absorber.

FIG. 1: XPS overview spectra recorded with Mg $K\alpha$ excitation of differently treated CIGS samples. From bottom to top: reference without KF PDT rinsed with DI water, reference without KF PDT etched in HCl, KF PDT treated sample rinsed with DI water, KF PDT treated sample etched in HCl.

FIG. 2: a) In $3d_{5/2}$ and b) Cu $2p_{3/2}$ XPS spectra with Mg $K\alpha$ excitation (1253.5 eV) of the CIGS absorber with and without KF PDT after rinsing in DI H_2O . c) and d) Comparison of the Cu $2p_{3/2}$ / In $3d_{5/2}$ XPS peak intensity ratio for both samples for different excitation energies (c): Mg $K\alpha$ excitation (1253.6 eV), d) synchrotron excitation (2100 eV) (~ 150 Words)

The HIKE setup also allows the measurement of the valence band region with sufficient resolution. Scans across the binding energy from 22 eV to 0 eV are displayed in Fig. 3. The position of the In $4d_{5/2}$ core level at 17.6 eV [14] is used as energy reference for both spectra: the In 4d doublets were fitted with Voigt functions and the energy scale was shifted to match the fitted peak positions with the In $4d_{5/2}$ core level. This way the position of the onset of the valence band structure of both samples can be directly compared excluding charging and band bending effects. The inset in Fig. 3 shows the magnified valence band edge (VBE) region for the untreated and the KF treated sample. A clear shift of the valence band onset of 0.37 eV is observed as a consequence of the KF PDT. We interpret the lowering of the valence band edge as a widening of the absorber band gap near the surface as a consequence of the Cu-depletion. This interpretation has also consequences on the

electronic behavior of the devices and will be discussed in more detail in the following paragraph. We confirmed the valence band shift for samples measured in the laboratory UPS setup, where the valence band edge is referenced to the Fermi energy and where two KF treated samples also showed a shift of the valence band edge of 0.3 eV – 0.4 eV with respect to the untreated references. In contrast to this, no shift of the effective bulk band gap (1.12 eV +/- 0.01 eV) is observed in quantum efficiency measurements of the devices, which confirms the assumption that the observed band gap widening is not a bulk effect but limited to the surface.

FIG. 3: XPS spectra with synchrotron excitation (2100 eV) of CIGS absorbers after rinsing with DI water. Red circles: CIGS absorber without KF PDT. Blue line: CIGS absorber after KF PDT. The energy scale of the spectra is referenced to the In $4d_{5/2}$ core level at 17.6 eV (dashed vertical line). The inset is a magnification of the valence band onset and shows a valence band shift of 0.37 eV for the KF PDT samples as compared to the untreated CIGS reference as obtained from linear extrapolation. (150 Words)

Discussion

It is a well-established fact that CIGS thin films with the considered CGI of 0.8 generally show a Cu-poor surface composition in XPS measurements [15,16]. Liao et al. [17] and Mönig et al. [18] attributed this to a reconstructed surface where the very topmost atom layers (monolayers) are completely depleted of Cu. Hence, if we already assume a Cu-depleted surface already for the untreated CIGS reference sample, the further decrease of the Cu signal after the KF PDT would mean that the Cu depleted region is extended further into the absorber. Taking into account that the difference between the laboratory and synchrotron measurements results in different IMFP of the photoelectrons, we expect this region now to be a few nanometers wide. Although a clear decrease of the Cu concentration at the surface of the KF PDT treated samples could be verified, a more detailed depth profiling of the composition needs more sophisticated analysis and measurement methods and is still pending. The fact that we are able to resolve changes in the position of the VBE relative to the core levels also

contributes to the hypothesis that the KF PDT alters the composition of a surface region which is extended into the bulk instead of being restricted only to the topmost atomic layers.

Jaffe et al. showed that the VBE of bulk CuInSe₂ is characterized by bonding and anti-bonding states formed by Cu *d* and Se *p* orbitals [19]. The strong *p-d* repulsion pushes the VBE towards the conduction band and results in lower band gaps as compared to corresponding II-VI semiconductors. Removal of Cu atoms diminishes this repulsion and the VBE collapses as a consequence, resulting in higher band gaps for compounds with a higher amount of Cu vacancies [20].

The potentially beneficial effect of an ordered vacancy compound (OVC) or ordered defect compound phases (ODC) on the electronic properties of chalcopyrite solar cells has been widely discussed in the past [21]. In particular, the increased distance of the valence band edge to the Fermi level and consequently the reduced concentration of holes as recombination partners at the CIGS surface may effectively impede interface recombination.

Here we show for the first time evidence for a valence band shift at the absorber surface as a result of the Cu depletion induced by the KF treatment. We interpret this shift as a band gap widening under the assumption of a constant position of the conduction band edge (CBE). The formation of a Cu-deficient phase near the absorber surface as a consequence of the KF PDT could lead to a reduced interface recombination in line with the discussion above.

CIGS devices with highest efficiency are normally prepared with a Cu-poor final composition and a GGI between 0 and 0.3. They are generally considered to be dominated by recombination in the bulk, which seems to contradict the suggested strong influence of the absorber surface on device performance. The type inversion suggested by Pianezzi et al [10] would also mainly affect the interface recombination, instead of the bulk recombination. Highest efficiency devices, where the dominating recombination takes place in the bulk should therefore benefit less from surface modifications in the first order. The contrary is observed [2,3,8] and might be explained by the following argument: Potassium can be expected to diffuse along grain boundaries analogous to sodium. Then, the described Cu depletion phenomena might also play a similar role at grain boundaries (GBs) within the absorber. As a consequence, KF PDT might help to reduce bulk recombination via stronger Cu depleted GBs. The beneficial effect of a Cu depletion at the GBs was suggested by Zunger et al. in reference [20]. Devices dominated by interface recombination with Cu rich absorbers, wide gap chalcopyrites or even kesterite absorbers should benefit stronger from the described effect and should be within the focus of further investigations. Newest findings of a shift towards higher performances for KF PDT treated samples with increased Ga contents seem to support this hypothesis [3].

The efficiency of the presented devices is with 14 % not very high and we suspect detrimental recombination also at the absorber surface. Therefore the observed strong increase in the V_{OC} of the KF treated devices is in line with the suggested

reduced interface recombination as outlined above. Nevertheless, the overall efficiency of these devices does not profit from the KF PDT due to a decrease in fill factor. We suspect surface oxidation of the absorbers as a result of the *ex situ* KF preparation to be the origin of this decrease. This hypothesis is supported by the extremely hygroscopic nature of KF which is expected to enable the efficient capture of moisture during the short air exposure necessary for sample transfer. For samples with increased air exposure time (hours to days) we observed even more severely decreased fill factors well below 30%. We conclude that for future investigations an *in situ* KF PDT would be preferable.

Conclusion

Summarizing the results, we could show that a potassium fluoride post deposition treatment of Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ absorbers grown on Na-containing substrates has a strong impact on their surface conditions in compositional as well as electronic terms. We confirmed with XPS that the KD PDT induces a strong Cu depletion at the very near absorber surface region. This surface modification has a direct influence on solar cell performance leading to an open circuit voltage increase of 60-70 mV. We attribute this to an altered band structure and efficiently reduced interface recombination losses. The band structure modification could be resolved through HAXPES measurements with an excitation at 2100 eV, showing a clear lowering of the valence band edge by 0.37 eV for KF treated samples. These findings emphasize the potential of the newly induced KF PDT for the improvement of chalcopyrite and related solar cells and give new insight into the underlying mechanisms behind it. This new opportunity in surface tuning opens new fields for further improvements of a variety of different material classes including wide-gap and Cu-rich grown chalcopyrite absorbers.

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